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The Influence of Production Resources on Innovation of Automobile Industry in Kenya

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Abstract

The study sought to find the influence of production resources on innovation of the automobile industry in Kenya. The study established that innovation of the automobile industry in Kenya was significantly influenced by technological knowledge and skills, financial resources, and the cost of production resources on innovation of the automobile industry in Kenya. The analysis was done by applying Statistical Package for Social Sciences (Version 25). Shown by the multiple regression analysis of 80% shown on table 5. The validity model shown in table 5 indicates that the model is valid ($F=.87.159$, $P=0.000$) implying that it can be used for purposes of prediction. The coefficient model shows the following in table 5: Technological and knowledge skills, 11.4 % ($B=0.127$), financial resources, 51.9% ($B=0.158$), cost of resources 16.5% ($B=0.143$). Otherwise all independent variables (Technological knowledge and skills, financial resources and cost of resources) remaining constant innovation of the automobile industry in Kenya remains at constant (26.3%. According to the bivariate analysis, the coefficient of correlation "r" for Technological knowledge and skills is equal to 0.753 ($P=0.000$), financial resources is equal to 0.797 ($p=0.000$), and cost of resources is equal to 0.855 ($P=0.000$). This demonstrates that the dependent variable (Innovation of automobile industry) and the independent variables have positive significance. This therefore underscores that all null hypotheses were rejected and the alternative hypotheses accepted since the independent variables in the study positively influence innovation of the automobile industry in Kenya.

Keywords: Cost of production resources, Technological knowledge and skills, Financial resources, Innovation of automobile industry

1. Introduction

Innovation of organizations is very important and complicated characteristics firms are faced in the contemporary globe. Innovativeness crucially impact establishment's performance together with viability. In order for an organization to achieve competitiveness to surpass its competitors increase its penetration of the market by the production of modern and distinctive goods for customers, it must be innovative. Profitability will be increased when an organization possesses the capability of innovation. Innovation is a characteristic which strongly dictates its performance. In addition, the functions of inward reorganizations, advancement in the technological development, returns, and value of society are considered as principal factors of innovation (Shaharoun et al., 2019). According to Santos and Paganotti (2018) on the innovative process in the automobile sector. Innovation process management is well articulated by co-creation as transformational innovation, and by innovation that is developed internally by a firm. The information from the study guided the creation, growth and application of many automobiles emanating from international frameworks, having domestic technological establishment centre's programs. In view of that fact, the transformation paradigm

within the domestic motor vehicle group participation forms a modification that was derived from research and development centre emanating from the headquarters. Bharawadwaj (2015) stated that the motor vehicle sector is changing in different directions; scientific knowledge, accommodation of tough state regulatory frameworks and organizational modifications together with dynamic customer requirements. Kenya has also diffused, commercialized and managed automobile technology over the years before and after independence. There have been some effective attempts to innovate and commercialize the automobile industry in Kenya. Mobias and the Nyayo car have been developed and produced in Kenya, only that they have not entered the global market. These interventions have not had any significant effect.

Automobile sector has become a pillar and a main driver of the global economy, and has reached the global market. It has disseminated technology through technology transfer, technology commercialization, and technology diffusion in form of processes, embedded into products, technical knowledge and skills. The motor vehicle industry forms the biggest manufacturing zone worldwide comprising very developed mass production operation on all parts of the numerous ranks of its central together with correlated distribution network. Attributed to internalization, the motor vehicle industry resulted into the most combined to automobile producing array spreading over continents thereby creating a section of worldwide distribution network surpassing intercontinental borders (Barnes & 2017. Showi, (2018), observed that the advancement of the automotive sector can be traced back to the year 1808, when the earliest car that used a heat engine in where combustion occurred in the engine and powered by hydrogen. It was regarded as the first production since Benz made many other similar copies. With the enlargement in number of production space, the automotive sector is also adding to the employment chances, contributing in satisfying the employment requirements of a young nation. Shaikh, (2013) stated that, the automotive sector basically flourished from World War II (1938-1945), for supplying automobiles used in the war. Since then, motor vehicle design experienced the total radical changes. Motor vehicle design and production finally came from the military inclination and other shadow of war in 1949. The sector kept on prospering at an amazing rate of innovative ideas and initiation of new technology. Shvetsova, (2019) stated that the motor vehicle sector is a big segment which needs a large type of firms to do mass manufacturing with a high performance and great influence over the economy of the nation. Across the world from 1910s to date; over a century, global automotive manufacturing in Europe, and the American automobile industry has been controlled by Big Three; Ford, General Motors, and Chrysler. Thus therefore, automobile industry manufacturing in the upcoming countries will have to diffuse automobile science and technology knowhow from the developed to developing countries so as to narrow the automobile scientific knowhow gaps and change the process from growth of industry to capabilities of innovation. Kastensson, (2014), noted that, the first mass-produced cars were offered for sale at the beginning of 20th century. The manufacture of Ford and Budd's all-steel body, came up with many pros from the perspectives both being a process and as well as a product, and was a necessary condition for the mass production of cars. Product lifecycles, has at the same time been reduced by the demand for new products, which has resulted into mergers and takeovers. This has resulted into sharing of investments, and caused platform growth necessitating automakers to share components. McLennan and Black (2016) noted that from the start of this century, Africa south of the Saharan developed quickly due to increase of the mid-level class which as a matter of fact has increased the demand for automobiles though at a lower level. It is also important to note that outside South Africa, domestic production is small. The degree of industrialization in various regions in Africa south of the Saharan is remarkably low and also production abilities are minimal. Domestic production in countries like Nigeria and Kenya is inspired by formulation of automobile policies. Makundi, (2017) noted that commercial manufacture of automobiles in the country of Kenya started seriously in the later half year of 1970's. Five manufacturing firms were introduced under control of policies of the state which inspired import substitution and triggered industrial development within a short period. Together with western joint cooperation's, Kenya possessed principal shares in three assembly plants. Out of the five plants two stopped their operations in 1980's. It is estimated that the three surviving plants are not reaching the capacity since they produce approximately thirty percent capacity of their capacity. This increase was inspired by government policies of that day through application of trade package of tariffs compromise for assembly kits, high imposition of free trade tax for imported of complete kits brought from abroad and prime concern with forex allocation for the manufacturing industry at the time of forex control. Kenya Vehicle Manufacturers is the most underused compared to the three other firms. By 2015 it was using only three percent of its capacity.

There are challenges of formation of the country's motor vehicle makes in third world nations. The required automobile atmosphere is wanting and also users have low purchasing ability. Bomet and Wambua, (2020) stated that the automotive sector in Kenya is well developed as opposed to other countries in the East African region. In Kenya the sector was established in 1960 by Volkswagen which manufactured the Beatle. Leyland Kenya was started in corroboration with the government of Kenya and Leyland of United Kingdom in 1974. It was later in 1989 handed over to Kenya Vehicle Manufacturers Ltd. General Motors Kenya was started in corroboration with General Motors and the government of Kenya to the manufacture motor vehicles in 1975. However, production started after 1977. In 2003, General Motors Kenya was named to General Motors East Africa and again, it changed its name to be Isuzu East Africa in April 201. Valenzuela-Fernandez et al. (2021) stated that firms with strong organizational innovation capabilities are better positioned than their competitors to adapt, integrate, and transform internal competencies to respond to changes in their business environment. This ability enables them to create and capture value for both the firm and its clients, indicating that organizational innovation capability significantly influences innovation performance. Organizations require resources so as to be productive. Motor vehicles organizations in Kenya can adapt automobile technical knowledge and skills from technology transferred from developed countries, apply research and development resource and foreign direct investment resource to enhance innovation of the motor vehicle industry and design, manufacture and commercialize automobiles to domestic and global market.

2. Research objectives

The objective of the study includes: to determine the influence of the technological knowledge and skills, on innovation of the automobile industry, to evaluate the influence of financial resources on innovation of the automobile industry, to examine the influence of financial resources on innovation of the automobile industry, and to investigate the influence of cost of resources to the automobile industry on innovation of the automobile industry in Kenya.

Research Hypotheses

- i) **H₀**: Technological knowledge and skills of the work force has no statistical significance on innovation of the automobile industry in Kenya.
- ii) **H₀**: Financial resources has no statistical significance on innovation of the automobile industry in Kenya.
- iii) **H₀**: Coast of production resources has no statistical significance on innovation of the automobile industry in Kenya.

3. Literature Review

In a study by Valenzuela-Fernandez et al. (2021) on organizational innovation capabilities, the results demonstrated that firms with strong organizational innovation capabilities are better positioned than their competitors to adapt, integrate, and transform internal competencies to respond to changes in their business environment. This ability enables them to create and capture value for both the firm and its clients, indicating that organizational innovation capability significantly influences innovation performance. Larsson (2017) investigated on the features of production innovation and the research results revealed that the followed results of production innovation are largely cost reductions and adds in quality. Despite this, production innovation also contributes to an expansion of the product design space and enhances overall innovation capabilities, leading to the establishment of a sustainable competitive advantage. Furthermore, the successful implementation of production innovation is contingent upon navigating a complex process involving internal organizational factors, external customer dynamics, and various other actors within the production system. Mani (2011) conducted an extensive study within the Indian automobile industry titled "Augmenting Innovation Capacities through Internal and External Resources." This research delved deep into discerning the differential performance dynamics between domestic and multinational firms operating within this industry, with a specific focus on their innovative endeavors. What emerged from the findings was a distinct pattern: domestic companies predominantly drew from their internal resources to fuel

innovation, while multinational firms exhibited a more robust reliance on external sources. The implications of these findings were profound. They shed light on how the Indian automobile industry has evolved into one of the most innovative sectors within the country. The study showed that domestic firms have been more innovative, with their strategies focusing on both internal and external sources, including substantial investments in Research and Development (R&D). Julienti and Ahmad (2010) investigated the relationship between firm resources and product innovation performance. The research outcomes unveiled a multifaceted perspective on product innovation performance, encompassing a spectrum of dimensions. These included shifts in new product introductions, technical and technological attributes, market responsiveness, product quality, product development timelines, profitability, and market share. Notably, the study lent credence to the resource-based view, underscoring the significance of intangible resources, particularly the facet of "product reputation," as a pivotal indicator of product innovation performance. In their own investigation, Haneda and Ito (2018) embarked on an exploration of the intricate interplay between organizational and human resource management and innovation outcomes, with a specific focus on both product and process innovation. The findings suggest that implementing a diverse array of organizational and human resource management practices simultaneously significantly enhances the likelihood of product innovation. In essence, these results underscore the critical role of effective human resource management for research and development personnel in achieving innovation success. Furthermore, having board members actively engaged in the research and development framework and implementing strategic organizational changes, such as establishing or relocating research and development centers, are essential steps in fostering product innovation. In 2019, Okwemba conducted an extensive research investigation delving into how organizational capabilities shape the non-financial performance of manufacturing firms operating in Kenya. These analyses unveiled a significant and positive impact of various organizational capabilities, including technological, managerial, marketing, coordination, and knowledge management capabilities, on firm performance. Additionally, the study affirmed that managers' cognition acted as a mediating factor in the relationship between organizational capabilities and firm performance. In summary, the research demonstrated that organizational capabilities hold substantial sway over the non-financial performance of manufacturing firms in Kenya. Singh et al. (2018) conducted an investigation into the influence of diverse organizational capabilities on firm performance within the manufacturing industry. Their research endeavor had a core objective: to offer a comprehensive insight into the manner in which a spectrum of capabilities, encompassing Research and Development (R&D) capabilities, human resource aptitude, process innovation proficiency, product innovation prowess, and manufacturing capabilities, shape and influence the overall performance of organizations. The study's outcomes revealed a substantial and positive relationship between organizational capabilities and firm performance, with firm performance being evaluated based on two key variables: sales performance and financial performance. Notably, the findings underscored the significance of R&D capabilities and process innovation capabilities in enhancing sales performance, while superior financial performance was associated with process innovation capabilities and product innovation capabilities. Maina and Lavu (2019) conducted an investigation into the relationship between organizational resources and strategy implementation within non-profit organizations, using the Kenya Medical Research Institute (KWTRP) as a case study. Their research aimed to assess how financial resources and technological competencies impact the successful execution of strategic plans. The research findings provided evidence that human resources, financial resources, and technological competence significantly influenced the implementation of strategic plans at KWTRP. The study's conclusion emphasized the critical role of an organization's employees as valuable assets contributing to its overall efficiency. Furthermore, it highlighted the importance of effectively allocating financial resources, which, in turn, enables managers to create more productive and efficient teams, facilitates strategic planning, and ensures the availability of necessary resources for future endeavors. Technological competence enhances internal and external communication, streamlining organizational processes. Turning to the observations of Kuchia and Mburugu (2019), it is evident that substantial financial resources have been invested in community development to improve the living conditions of people. Projects deemed worth sustaining current value may not be the same in the future. Notwithstanding substantial spending in community-based services for young people and families, underinvestment and poor operations and maintenance, coupled with increased demand, have led to a concerning decline in the quality and availability of these services. Addressing this challenge necessitates

diversifying resource mobilization approaches to ensure the sustainability of existing rural community projects and the implementation of new initiatives for the broader community's benefit.

Methodology

Philosophy of the study

Study philosophies can be positivism, interpretivism, or pragmatism. Positivism, in its understanding of the world, operates on the premise that the external environment and the events of interest are objective entities, situated outside of and detached from the researcher, as asserted by Saunders et al. (2009). Positivism shows the belief that reality is firm and can be examined and explained from the objective point view unaccompanied by interfering with phenomena (Cresswell, Positivism is being considered the most specific technique for this research since it is appropriate for quantitative investigations as it is directed at describing causes which impact results and gives a bases for forecasting and generalization.

In the course of this study, the researcher opted for a survey research design, coupled with the application of bivariate and multiple regression analysis. The fundamental objective of such designs is, indeed, to establish a connection between variables, delineate the nature of this relationship, and quantify the extent of association between two variables. Specifically, multiple regression analysis will be harnessed to forecast the magnitude of the dependent variable. A survey design is appropriate for this study since data can be collected from respondents within various set ups of similar characteristic's in terms of their attitudes, perceptions, opinions, behaviours, or values (Sounders, 2012). This study employed a combination of quantitative and qualitative approaches in both data collection and analysis. As emphasized by Babbie (2010), the utilization of both quantitative and qualitative techniques fortifies the research endeavor. These approaches serve to articulate and direct the focus toward objective measurements and the quantitative evaluation of data. The variables of this study included: to determine the influence of the cost of production resources on innovation of the automobile industry, to evaluate the influence of technological knowledge and skills on innovation of the automobile industry, to examine the influence of financial resources on innovation of the automobile industry, and to investigate the influence of cost of entry to the automobile industry on innovation of the automobile industry in Kenya.

This study's target population was 140 automobile firms each having four members in this category: CEOs, Technical persons, Finance Managers and Sales managers forming a population of 560 members. The sampling frame for the target population will be automobile firms in Nairobi, Mombasa and Kisumu cities and Thika town. Stratified sampling technic was applied on automobile dealers. The dealers were stratified into four strata namely Nairobi City, Mombasa City, Kisumu and Thika Town. Random samples were chosen from each stratum employing the stratified sampling technique, with the sample size for each stratum determined by its proportion to the overall population and a systematic sampling technique was applied to select approximately a sample of 30% of the population as given by (Mugenda & Mugenda 2003). The 9 assemblers were considered in totality. In alignment with Mugenda and Mugenda, Kothari (2004) advocated for the suitability of a sample size ranging from 10% to 30%. Opting for a well-selected sample size of 30% facilitates meticulous observations and precise measurements, offering a higher level of accuracy compared to conducting research on a larger pool of automobile firms. This approach ensures that every automobile firm in every city and town has a known and equal likelihood of selection. To determine the sample size, the calculation was as follows: 30% of 131 amounts to 39, which, when added to the 9 assemblers, resulted into a total sample size of 48 automobile firms resulting into 192 respondents forming the sample size. The chief executive officers, the technical persons, the finance managers, and sales managers will be relevant for this research since they cut across the automobile firm's organizational structure and therefore understand the aspects of enterprise capabilities and innovation of automobile industry.

Consistency of study instrument is the level where a testing of event gives compatible and firm results. Even so, reliability of instrument also deals with itself all the time (Moser & Kalton, 2017). High internal consistency reliability is achieved when the items on a scale align and assess the same underlying construct (Robinson, 2019). The Cronbach Alpha Coefficient is a popular metric of consistency within, especially when Likert scales are used. An internal consistency coefficient of at least 0.70 is desirable. Validity

pertains to the extent to which these instruments effectively measure what they purport to measure or were originally designed to assess. It's important to note that reliability, on its own, falls short in ensuring the effectiveness of an assessment tool. A valid instrument is one which tests what is intended to test (Gliner et.al. 2016). Validity of a study instrument will be measured for internal Cronbach's Alpha based on a 70% level of acceptance was used to ensure consistency. This study strategy will satisfy standards of reliability and validity, yielding data that are both consistent (reliability) and correct (validity).

Pre-testing is testing a study instrument on a small sample of respondents singled out by the investigator before a full research is carried out, so as to identify any challenges e.g., unclear choice of words or the questionnaire taking a long time to be executed. Pretesting was done in Malindi Town. The researcher made adjustments to the questionnaires to withdraw ambiguity and double meanings after piloting. Adding to that, changes of the completion time for the questionnaire was made. During this procedure of data collection all ethical values regarding anonymity, confidentiality and respect of the respondents were highly considered by the researcher.

Quantitative data were entered into Statistical Package for Social Sciences version 25 (SPSS) so as to run descriptive and inferential statistics such as frequency and percentages. To assess the degree of association between two variables Pearson correlation and regression analysis were performed as emphasized by Casson and Farmer (2014). A correlation coefficient (r), served as an indicator of the relationship between the two variables under scrutiny. ANOVA f - test was applied to determine if there are statistically significant differences of two or more means. The relationship between corporate strategy and innovation of automobile firms from the obtained data, multiple linear regression analysis was applied. Mugenda and Mugenda (2012) stated that, such analysis endeavours to determine whether a set of variables foresee a particular dependent variable and in this way, strives to increase the accuracy of the estimate. Because this research has four independent factors, multiple regression model was applied. Innovation of automobile industry, was regressed against on four production resource variables namely, technological knowledge and skills, financial resources and cost of resources on innovation of the automobile industry in Kenya. The study conducted a multiple regression model and used it to predict the extent to which each of the four independent variables (X_1 , X_2 , X_3 , and X_4) and the one moderating variable (Z_1) influenced the dependent variable (Y).

Findings and Discussion

4.1 Introduction

The study sought to investigate the influence of production resources on innovation of the automobile industry in Kenya.

4.2 Demographic characteristics of the respondents and instruments reliability

The study was conducted in Kenya and focused on 48 automobile firms drawn from a pool of 140 such firms and each stratum essentially constituted a scaled-down representation of the overall sample of 48 automobile firms where the respondents were the CEOs, Technical managers, Finance Managers and Sales managers.

Response rate

A total of 151 responses were received out of a target population of 192 respondents. This represented 78.65% response rate and based on this response rate result therefore, it implied that the response rate was adequate for this study.

4.3 Respondents' characteristics

The study sought to determine the respondents' characteristics such as level of education, and period in the industry The results of respondents' characteristics were presented in as indicated accordingly.

4.3.1 Level of education

The respondents were requested to indicate the highest education. The results show that most of the respondents' highest Level of Education was bachelor degree accounted by 53% followed by diploma 41.7%. Those with post graduate accounted for 5.3% while school certificate showed 0%. This implies that the respondents are well educated and well understand the issues of the influence of enterprise capabilities on innovation of the automobile industry in Kenya.

4.3.2 Period in the industry

The respondents were also requested to indicate how long they have been in the industry. The results show that most (58.30%) of the have been in the industry for period between 1-10 years followed by 10-20 years which accounted for 37.70%.

Reliability instrument

Table 1: Cronbach Alpha for Reliability Assessments

Variables	Number of items	Cronbach Alpha Values
Technological Knowledge	5	0.857
Financial resources	5	0.719
Cost of resources	5	0.739
Innovation of automobile industry	5	0.855

As presented in Table 1, Cronbach alpha values for all the variables; technological knowledge and skills, Financial resources and cost of resources and Innovation of automobile industry were greater than 0.7. From these results it can be concluded that the constructs measured had the adequate reliability for the subsequent stages of analysis since all the Cronbach Alpha values were greater than 0.7.

Analytical Model Diagnostic Tests

Regression diagnostics are essential for identifying and confirming a robust predictive relationship between the dependent and independent variables. Several diagnostic tests were conducted, including assessments of goodness of fit, multicollinearity, correlation statistics, and tests for normality.

Multicollinearity Test

Table 2: Tolerance and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) Analysis

Model	Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	VIF
Technological Knowledge	.440	1.293
Financial resources	.637	3.108
Cost of resources	.382	2.132

Multicollinearity arises when multiple independent variables in the model are interconnected and offer duplicate information regarding the response variable. To determine how much the variance of predicted coefficients is increased as a result of collinearity between variables that are independent, this study employed Variance Inflation Factors (VIF). The results of Tolerance and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) Analysis for multicollinearity test are presented in Table 2 and is indicating that all the VIF are far less than 10

Test of data for normality

Table 3: Tests of Normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	Df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Technological Knowledge	.797	151	.290	.793	151	.339
Financial resources	.886	151	.320	.428	151	.180
Cost of resources	.755	151	.431	.686	151	.310
Innovation of automobile industry	.576	151	.561	.354	151	.072

*. This is a lower bound of the true significance.

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Normally data analysis is carried on assumption that data were sampled from a normal distributed data. The testing of data for normality of all the variables under study was done based on Shapiro-wilk (S-W) test and the results were presented in Table 3. The results indicated that the P-value of all the variables was greater than 0.05 (95% confidence level) implying that the variables did not deviate from the normal distribution.

Table 4. Bivariate Correlation analysis results

Variables		Innovation of automobile industry	Technological knowledge	Financial resources	Cost of resources
Innovation of automobile industry	Pearson Correlation	1			
	Sig. (2-tailed)				
	N	151			
Technological Knowledge	Pearson Correlation	.753**	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000			
	N	151	151		
Financial resources	Pearson Correlation	.797**	.923**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		
	N	151	151	151	
Cost of resources	Pearson Correlation	.755**	.853**	.918**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	151	151	151	151

A Bivariate Correlation analysis

The relationship between the study variables and results is depicted in Table 4. of the study's data using Correlation coefficient for Karl Pearson (r). In accordance with the findings, the dependent variable and the independent factors (Technological knowledge and skills, Financial resources and Cost of production resources) (Innovation of automobile industry) have a very significant positive connection. According to the analysis, the coefficient of correlation " r " for Technological knowledge and skills is equal to 0.753** ($P=0.000$), Financial resources is equal to 0.797** ($p=0.000$), and Cost of resources is equal to 0.755** ($P=0.000$). This demonstrates that the dependent variable (Innovation of automobile industry) and the independent variables (Technological knowledge and skills, financial resources and cost of production resources) have a highly significant positive association, with financial resources having the lead. Therefore, it follows that the automobile industry must follow the financial resources to the later.

- i) H_0 : Technological knowledge and skills of the work force has no statistical significance on innovation of the automobile industry in Kenya.
- ii) H_0 : Financial resources has no statistical significance on innovation of the automobile industry in Kenya.
- iii) H_0 : Cost of resources has no statistical significance on innovation of the automobile industry in Kenya.

Influence of production resources on innovation of the automobile industry

This research focused in assessing the influence of the various independent variables (Technological knowledge and skills, Financial resource, and Cost of resources) on the dependent variable (Innovation of the automobile industry). To achieve this, a multiple linear regression analysis was performed to test and explain the casual relationships between variables. The multiple linear regression model was composed of both the dependent and independent variables. The dependent variable of the study was on innovation of the automobile industry while the independent variables were; Technological knowledge and skills, financial resources and cost of resources. The model of the study is as shown in the equation.

Equation 4.1: A Multiple Linear Regression Model One

The multiple linear regression model for the study was as follows;

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \varepsilon$$

Where;

Y= Innovation of the automobile industry β_0 =constant β_i is the coefficient for X_i (i=1, 2, 3)

X_1 =

X_2 =

X_3 =

ε = Error Term

Table 5: Multiple linear regression results

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.800 ^a	.640	.633	.37362

a. Predictors: (Constant), Technological skills, Financial resources and Cost of resources

Validity model					
Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	36.500	3	12.167	87.159	.000 ^b
Residual	20.520	147	.140		
Total	57.020	150			
Technological skills	Financial resources	Cost of resources			

a. Dependent Variable: Innovation of the automobile industry

b. Predictors: (Constant),

Coefficients ^a					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error			
(Constant)	1.053	.263		4.010	.000
Technological skills	.114	.127	.115	.894	.373
Financial resources	.519	.158	.558	3.293	.001
Cost of resources	.165	.143	.144	1.156	.249

a. Dependent Variable: Innovation of the automobile industry

Results presented in the Table 5 show that there is a strong relationship (R=0.80, P=0.000) between enterprise capabilities (Technological knowledge and skills, financial resources and cost of resources) and Innovation of the automobile industry in Kenya.

This means that when enterprise capabilities (Technological knowledge and skills, financial resources and cost of production resources) are applied by automobile industry in Kenya, its relationship with Innovation of the automobile industry improves by 80%.

The validity model indicates that the model is valid (F=87.159, P=000) implying that it can be used for purposes of prediction. The coefficient model shows that for every unit increase of Technological knowledge and skills, innovation of the automobile industry improves by 11.4% (B=0.115), a unit increase in financial resources, innovation of the automobile industry improves by 51.9 % (B=0.558) and a unit increase in cost of resources innovation of the automobile industry improves by 16.5%(B=0.144). Otherwise all independent variables (Technological knowledge and skills, financial resources and cost of resources) remaining constant innovation of the automobile industry in Kenya remains at constant (105.3%.

Below are the null hypotheses tested?

Testing of Hypothesis One

H₀: Technological knowledge and skills, has no statistical significance on innovation of the automobile industry in Kenya.

The results on table 4. shows a strong positive correlation coefficient of 0.753 which is statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). This leads to rejecting the null hypothesis and accepting the alternate hypothesis that technological skills has statistical significance influence on innovation of the automobile industry in Kenya. This means that on overall, technological skills is positively related to innovation of the automobile firms in Kenya. The study results concur with the study by Julienti and Ahmad (2010) who investigated the relationship between firm resources and product innovation performance. The study employed established techniques for business research scale development and questionnaire design. Respondents received self-developed questionnaires via mail, allowing them to assess and respond within their office environments. The research outcomes unveiled a multifaceted perspective on product innovation performance, encompassing a spectrum of dimensions. These included shifts in new product introductions, technical and technological attributes, market responsiveness, product quality, product development timelines, profitability, and market share. Notably, the study lent credence to the resource-based view, underscoring the significance of intangible resources, particularly the facet of "product reputation," as a pivotal indicator of product innovation performance. Again the study findings agree with the study done by Haneda and Ito (2018) who embarked on an exploration of the intricate interplay between organizational and human resource management and innovation outcomes, with a specific focus on both product and process innovation. The findings suggest that implementing a diverse array of organizational and human resource management practices simultaneously significantly enhances the likelihood of product innovation. These findings remained consistent when considering breakthrough innovation, which underscores the technological superiority of products. In essence, these results underscore the critical role of effective human resource management for research and development personnel in achieving innovation success. Furthermore, having board members actively engaged in the research and development framework and implementing strategic organizational changes, such as establishing or relocating research and development centers, are essential steps in fostering product innovation.

H₀: Financial resources has no statistical significance on innovation of the automobile industry in Kenya. The results on table 4. show a strong positive correlation coefficient of 0.797 which is statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). This leads to rejecting the null hypothesis and accepting the alternate hypothesis that creativity of the work force has statistical significance influence on innovation of the automobile industry in Kenya. This means that on overall, financial resources is positively related to innovation of the automobile firms in Kenya. These findings concur with the results of Maina and Lavu (2019) who conducted an investigation into the relationship between organizational resources and strategy implementation within non-profit organizations, using the Kenya Medical Research Institute (KWTRP) as a case study. Their research aimed to assess how financial resources and technological competencies impact the successful execution of strategic plans. The research findings provided evidence that human resources, financial resources, and technological competence significantly influenced the implementation of strategic plans at KWTRP. Furthermore, it highlighted the importance of effectively allocating financial resources, which, in turn, enables managers to create more productive and efficient teams, facilitates strategic planning, and ensures the availability of necessary resources for future endeavors. The study results concur with the findings of Valenzuela-Fernandez et al. (2021) who investigated on organizational innovation capabilities, the results demonstrated that firms with strong organizational innovation capabilities are better positioned than their competitors to adapt, integrate, and transform internal competencies to respond to changes in their business environment. This ability enables them to create and capture value for both the firm and its clients, indicating that organizational innovation capability significantly influences innovation performance. Turning to the observations of Kuchia and Mburugu (2019), it is evident that substantial financial resources have been invested in community development to improve the living conditions of people. However, the effectiveness of aid delivery has become a growing concern for the donor community. Development practitioners have shifted from project-oriented approaches to more comprehensive strategies, Sector-wide strategies, restructuring policies, alleviating poverty strategies, program-based methods, and budgetary assistance are some examples, with the aim of reducing fragmentation in development systems and changing the way aid is disbursed. Projects deemed worth sustaining current value may not be the same in the future. Notwithstanding substantial spending in community-based services for young people and families,

underinvestment and poor operations and maintenance, coupled with increased demand, have led to a concerning decline in the quality and availability of these services. Addressing this challenge necessitates diversifying resource mobilization approaches to ensure the sustainability of existing rural community projects and the implementation of new initiatives for the broader community's benefit.

H₀: Cost of production resources has no statistical significance on innovation of the automobile industry in Kenya.

The results on table 4. show a strong positive correlation coefficient of 0.755 which is statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). This leads to rejecting the null hypothesis and accepting the alternate hypothesis that Technological patents has statistical significance influence on innovation of the automobile industry in Kenya. This means that on overall, cost of resources is positively related to innovation of the automobile firms in Kenya. The study results correspond with the findings of Larsson (2017) who investigated on the features of production innovation and the research results revealed that the followed results of production innovation are largely cost reductions and adds in quality. Despite this, production innovation also contributes to an expansion of the product design space and enhances overall innovation capabilities, leading to the establishment of a sustainable competitive advantage. Furthermore, the successful implementation of production innovation is contingent upon navigating a complex process involving internal organizational factors, external customer dynamics, and various other actors within the production system. The study results also agree with the findings of Maina and Lavu (2019) who conducted an investigation into the relationship between organizational resources and strategy implementation within non-profit organizations, using the Kenya Medical Research Institute (KWTRP) as a case study. Their research aimed to assess how financial resources and technological competencies impact the successful execution of strategic plans. The research findings provided evidence that human resources, financial resources, and technological competence significantly influenced the implementation of strategic plans at KWTRP. Furthermore, it highlighted the importance of effectively allocating financial resources, which, in turn, enables managers to create more productive and efficient teams, facilitates strategic planning, and ensures the availability of necessary resources for future endeavors.

Conclusion

The study was to determine the influence of production resources on the innovation of the automobile industry in Kenya. The researcher established that (Technological knowledge and skills, Financial resources and Cost of resources) had a significant influence on innovation of the automobile industry in Kenya. Shown by the multiple regression analysis table 5. $R = 80\%$. The validity model shown in table 5 indicates that the model is valid ($F = .87.159$, $P = 0.000$) implying that it can be used for purposes of prediction. The coefficient model shows the following in table 5: Technological and knowledge skills, 11.4 % ($B = 0.127$), financial resources, 51.9% ($B = 0.158$), cost of resources 16.5% ($B = 0.143$). Otherwise all independent variables (Technological knowledge and skills, financial resources and cost of production resources) remaining constant innovation of the automobile industry in Kenya remains at constant (26.3%. According to the bivariate analysis, the coefficient of correlation "r" for Technological knowledge and is equal to 0.753 ($P = 0.000$), financial resources is equal to 0.797 ($p = 0.000$), and cost of production resources is equal to 0.855 ($P = 0.000$). This demonstrates that the dependent variable (Innovation of automobile industry) and the independent variables have positive significance. This therefore underscores that all null hypotheses were rejected and the alternative hypotheses accepted since the independent variables in the study positively influence innovation of the automobile industry in Kenya.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the management of automobile firms should develop good mechanisms to align their business operations with the current dynamics i.e. adoption of innovation so as to apply new technologies, new techniques and new processes in order to enhance innovation so as to come up with their own automobile brands and commercialize them in the global market. The management should incorporate production resources innovation strategies, technological research and amass automobile production resources in order to enhance innovation of the automobile industry. The government should enact laws and formulate policies that will create an enabling environment for the automobile industry to incorporate innovation so as to come up with their own automobile brands and commercialize them in the global market.

The remaining factors of 20% have not been explained by the study leaving room for further research to be conducted.

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